

A New Gravimetric Method for the Estimation of Lead.

I. Purely from its soluble salts.

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When a solution of lead nitrate is treated with alkaline hydrogen peroxide, an orange colored precipitate of the empirical composition $Pb_3O_7, 3H_2O$ is obtained. This was first noticed by Brauner (*Zeit. anorg. Chem.*, 1894, 7, 2) who considered it as a definite compound.

We have however observed that except when the alkalis, sodium or potassium hydroxide used, are very weak, the precipitation is never complete; on the other hand, if sodium or potassium hydroxide solution be replaced by ammonium hydroxide, the precipitation of lead becomes quantitative. This observation serves as the basis of a quantitative estimation of lead from solution of its salts, which forms the subject matter of the present paper.

The influence of the presence of salts such as potassium nitrate, ammonium acetate, sodium acetate, and ammonium nitrate on the precipitation has been studied and the colour of the precipitates in each case has been found to vary somewhat gradually from orange red, in the case of pure lead salt solution, to yellow in the presence of the respective salts. The precipitation in presence of different salts is quantitative, when the concentration (gms. per 100 c.c.) in each case does not exceed the amount stated below:—1 gm. for ammonium acetate, 15 gms. for potassium nitrate, 8 gms. for sodium acetate, and 4 gms. for ammonium nitrate.

The precipitate having the composition $Pb_3O_7, 3H_2O$ is quite stable even when dried at 180° . Excess of hydrogen peroxide has somewhat dissolving action on the precipitate and changes it into lead hydroxide. It is soluble in excess of caustic alkalis but insoluble in ammonium hydroxide. Excess of alkali and ammonium salts has also got a solvent action. Hence in actual estimation of lead by this method, the volume of the solution should be kept such that the concentration of the ammonium salt formed during the process does not exceed the values specified above and also an excess of ammonia should in each case be employed.

The present method can claim advantage over the recently described method of Spacu and Dick (*Z. anal. Chem.*, 1927, **72**, 289) in the fact that it is possible to estimate lead in a solution containing larger amounts of the same and even when it is present as an acetate.

Further work on the subject specially regarding the nature of the precipitates in presence of the nitrates and acetates of alkalis and ammonia and the possibility of separating and estimating lead in presence of other metals is in progress.

EXPERIMENTAL.

The best condition for obtaining the crystalline precipitate of $Pb_5O_7 \cdot 3H_2O$ from lead nitrate or acetate solution is to add one or two drops of dilute nitric or acetic acid and then to dilute to a considerable volume with water, then 2 c. c. of 3% hydrogen peroxide are added for nearly 0.1 g. of lead present in the solution, stirred well and finally 2 c. c. of concentrated ammonia are added at a time for the same amount of lead. The mixture is stirred well and then on heating over water-bath for 20 minutes, stirring occasionally or on boiling for 5 to 7 minutes, it is allowed to settle. By this the flocculent and bulky precipitate as obtained in the cold changes to a scaly crystalline condition. The clear liquid over the precipitate is as far as possible decanted through a Jena glass silica-bed crucible (3/5-7) fitted in a filtering flask and a slow suction is maintained by mouth during the filtration, care being taken that as little as possible of the precipitate comes on the bed of the crucible; otherwise it clogs the pores of it and renders the filtration and washing of the precipitate difficult, thus causing much hindrance to the rapidity of the method. The precipitate is washed by decantation with 50 c. c. of warm water several times till the wash water is free from nitrate or acetate as the case may be. The whole of the precipitate is then transferred into the crucible with a little water, and finally the precipitate is washed with absolute alcohol and sucked well. The final washing with alcohol may be avoided, in that case the crucible with the precipitate is dried for a longer time (about an hour). The washed precipitate is then dried at 110° - 120° for half an hour and weighed. During the time of weighing it was observed that the precipitate slowly increased in weight; probably this is due to the slow absorption of moisture by it. Hence the weighing should be finished within a minute or two.

For this, a second weight is taken after the usual heating and cooling. With higher amounts of lead as in Experiment No. 15, 100 c.c. of warm water are used each time for washing by decantation. In this case some 8 to 10 times' washing is required to free the precipitate from ammonium nitrate and also the precipitate takes a greater time for drying; to be sure here, the heating, cooling and weighing are carried a third time.

Solutions of pure lead nitrate and acetate were prepared and their respective strengths were determined by the sulphate method. In the solutions lead was estimated according to the present method. The results of the analyses are tabulated below.

Results.

No.	Lead nitrate solution taken (c.c.)	C.c. of hydrogen peroxide added.	C.c. of conc. ammonia added.	Weight of the precipitate.	Found Pb cal from $Pb_3O_7, 3H_2O$	Pb present (estimated by sulphate method).	% of error.
					$\text{Log F} \left(\frac{\text{Pb}}{Pb_3O_7, 3H_2O} \right)$		
					$= \bar{1}.9354.$		
1	5	2	2	0.1163 g.	0.1002 g.	0.0995 g.	0.7
2	5	2	2	0.1160	0.09999	„	0.5
3	5	2	2	0.1154	0.09945	„	0.05
4	5	2	2	0.1164	0.1003	„	0.8
5	5	2	2	0.1156	0.09963	„	0.13
6	5	2	2	0.1150	0.0991	„	0.4
7	21	8	8	0.4872	0.4199	0.4179	0.5
8	1	1	1	0.0228	0.01964	0.0199	1.3
9	1	1	1	0.0232	0.01999	„	0.45
10	1	1	1	0.0235	0.02025	„	1.75
11	2	1	1	0.0460	0.03965	0.0398	0.4
12	2	2	2	0.0463	0.03990	„	0.25
13	3	2	2	0.0696	0.05998	0.0597	0.47
14	5	2	2	0.1205	0.1039	0.1035	0.38
15	50	20	20	1.2010	1.035	1.035	0.0
16	5 (acetate)	2	2	0.1037	0.08935	0.08937	0.02
17	10 „	4	4	0.2068	0.1782	0.1787	0.3

The results as shown in the table are evidently satisfactory. The method is excellent where the amount of lead present gives the weight of precipitate in the first decimal place of the grammes.

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